

Solid-medium bioassay for screening nematicidal activity of microbial strains using *Panagrellus redivivus*

Diego Sauka*, Augusto Salas

¹ Instituto Nacional de Tecnología Agropecuaria (INTA), Instituto de Microbiología y Zoolología Agrícola (IMYZA), Hurlingham 1686, Argentina.

² Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET), Ciudad Autónoma de Buenos Aires 1425, Argentina.

*E-mail: sauka.diego@inta.gob.ar

Abstract

This protocol describes a preliminary solid-medium bioassay for evaluating the nematicidal activity of microbial strains using *Panagrellus redivivus* (Panagrolaimidae) as a model organism. The assay is based on the direct exposure of nematodes to microbial lawns growing on solid culture medium. Mortality is determined by microscopic observation after incubation under controlled conditions. The method is useful for the preliminary screening of microorganisms with potential applications in biological control and agricultural bioinputs.

1. Introduction

Several microorganisms of agricultural interest produce metabolites and bioactive compounds capable of affecting nematode viability. These activities may involve toxins, enzymes, diffusible metabolites, surface-associated compounds, or other mechanisms associated with microbial growth.

The evaluation of nematicidal activity using solid-medium bioassays represents a simple and rapid strategy for the preliminary identification of microbial strains with potential use as biological control agents and bioinputs. In this assay, nematodes are placed directly onto microbial lawns grown on agar plates, allowing direct interaction between both organisms under controlled conditions.

Panagrellus redivivus is frequently used as a model nematode because it is easy to maintain under laboratory conditions and allows rapid evaluation of biological activity.

2. Objective

To preliminarily evaluate the nematicidal activity of microbial strains using *P. redivivus* as a model organism in a solid-medium bioassay.

3. Principle of the method

The method consists of exposing *P. redivivus* nematodes directly to microbial lawns growing on solid medium plates. During incubation, nematodes interact with microbial cells and their associated metabolites. Mortality is evaluated microscopically and compared with negative controls lacking microbial inoculation.

4. Materials and equipment

Materials

- 90 mm Petri dishes.
- 15 mL Falcon tubes.
- Glass test tubes with caps.
- Microscope slides.
- Micropipettes.
- Sterile 20-200 μ L pipette tips.
- Pasteur pipettes.
- 1 μ L calibrated inoculating loop.
- Parafilm™.

Equipment

- Laminar flow cabinet.
- Optical microscope.
- Autoclave.
- Bacteriological incubator.
- Bunsen burner or lighter.

5. Culture media

The culture medium used for microbial growth should be selected according to the physiological requirements of the microorganism under evaluation in order to promote adequate biomass production and metabolite synthesis.

Different media may be used depending on the microbial strain, including:

- Nutrient Agar (NA),
- TSA (Tryptic Soy Agar),
- PDA (Potato Dextrose Agar) for filamentous fungi,
- or other appropriate media.

6. Preparation of nematodes

1. Prepare a suspension of *P. redivivus* in sterile distilled water.
2. Adjust the concentration to approximately 2000 nematodes per 100 μ L.
3. To estimate concentration:
 - Place 10 μ L of the suspension onto a lightly flame-sterilized microscope slide.
 - Count nematodes under an optical microscope at 10X magnification.
4. Sterile conditions are not required during this step.

7. Preparation of bacterial suspension

1. Prepare a bacterial suspension in 5 mL of sterile saline solution.
2. Adjust turbidity to the equivalent of a 0.5 McFarland standard.

8. Experimental procedure

8.1 Preparation of bacterial lawns

1. Using a calibrated 1 μ L inoculating loop, collect one loopful of the bacterial suspension.
2. Inoculate onto small Petri dishes containing the appropriate culture medium for the bacterial strain under evaluation.
3. Spread the inoculum by lawn inoculation.
4. Prepare three replicates per bacterial strain.

5. Using a calibrated 1 μL inoculating loop, collect one loopful of the bacterial suspension.
6. Inoculate 90 mm Petri dishes containing the appropriate culture medium to obtain confluent bacterial lawns.
7. Incubate plates at 29 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for at least 48 h or longer depending on bacterial growth characteristics.
8. Prepare three replicates per bacterial strain.

8.2 Negative control

1. Prepare three control plates containing uninoculated culture medium.

8.3 Nematode inoculation

1. Inoculate 100 μL of the nematode suspension onto the bacterial lawn surface of each treatment or control plate.

Figure 1. Experimental procedure for the evaluation of nematocidal activity on bacterial lawns using *P. redivivus*.

Bacterial lawns are prepared on 90 mm Petri dishes containing the appropriate culture medium for the bacterial strain under evaluation and incubated until confluent growth is obtained. Negative control plates consist of uninoculated culture medium inoculated only with the nematode suspension. Subsequently, 100 μL of the *P. redivivus* suspension are inoculated onto the surface of each bacterial lawn or control plate. Mortality is evaluated by microscopic observation.

9. Incubation

1. Incubate plates at the appropriate temperature for microbial growth, generally around 29 °C.
2. A 24 h incubation period is used for preliminary screening assays.

10. Mortality evaluation

1. Assess nematode mortality after incubation.
2. Observe 20 fields per Petri dish under an optical microscope (20X).
3. Record:
 - number of live nematodes;
 - number of dead nematodes.
4. Nematodes showing no detectable movement should be considered dead.

11. Data analysis

Nematicidal activity is determined by comparing mortality observed in bacterial treatments against the negative control.

It is recommended to:

- perform at least three independent experiments;
- calculate mortality percentages;
- correct mortality data using Abbott's formula when necessary;
- reject and repeat assays with control mortality higher than 10%;
- express results as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM).

12. Critical considerations

- Ensure homogeneous microbial growth among plates.
- Avoid excessive dehydration of agar media.
- Use fresh and actively growing microbial cultures.
- Maintain consistent nematode density among treatments.
- Biological activity may vary according to:

- culture medium,
- temperature,
- bacterial density,
- strain physiology,
- incubation time.

13. Expected results

Bacterial strains with nematicidal activity are expected to induce significantly higher mortality of *P. redivivus* compared to negative controls after 24 h of incubation.

14. Applications

This method may be used for:

- screening microorganisms with nematicidal potential;
- preliminary evaluation of microbial bioinputs;
- biocontrol strain selection;
- functional characterization of agricultural microorganisms;
- potential adaptation for filamentous fungi with nematicidal activity, although not yet validated.

15. Notes and troubleshooting

- Excess moisture may interfere with nematode visualization.
- Overgrown bacterial cultures may complicate mortality assessment.
- Incubation conditions should always be adjusted according to microbial physiology.
- The same observer should preferably perform mortality evaluations to minimize variability.

16. Biosafety considerations

- Handle microorganisms according to institutional biosafety guidelines.
- Inactivate live nematodes by heat treatment (72 °C for 30 min) before disposal.
- Discard biological waste in appropriate biohazard containers according to institutional regulations.

- Use appropriate personal protective equipment.

17. Keywords

Bioinputs; biological control; Panagrellus redivivus; nematicidal activity; bacterial screening; sustainable agriculture; biocontrol microorganisms.